

variance for all the traits (except kernel length after cooking and linear elongation ratio) indicated the predominance of additive gene action (Table 1).

IR50 possessed desirable GCA effects for kernel length, kernel breadth, kernel

thickness, L-B ratio, kernel length after cooking, kernel breadth after cooking, and linear elongation ratio. IR50 was found to be the best parent because of its desirable GCA effects for five traits (Table 2). ADT39 was the next best

parent. IR50 and ADT39 could be used in hybridization programs for improving grain quality traits through recombination breeding and for getting desirable segregants. ■

Breeding methods

Heterosis for kernel characters in rice

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Information is limited on the extent of heterosis for kernel characters in rice. We studied the heterotic manifestations of four kernel characters in 15 hybrids involving eight parents.

The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications during 1991-92 wet season (Oct-Feb) at TNRRI. Each genotype (parents and hybrids) was planted in two 3-m rows at 30- × 20-cm spacing. Observations were recorded for 10 randomly selected plants per replication.

Seeds were hulled in a McGill sample sheller. Kernel length and L-B ratio were measured with a Mitutoyo micrometer. Grain was milled in a Kett rice polisher and cooked by the method of Juliano and Perez. Kernel elongation was computed as the ratio of mean length of cooked rice to that of milled rice. The performance of hybrids over mid-parent (di) and better parent (dii) was estimated following standard procedures.

Heterosis for kernel length was low. Improved White Ponni/ADT41 and IR50/Kasturi expressed significant and positive relative heterosis. Heterosis for kernel L-B ratio was significant and negative, indicating that none of the hybrids were superior for grain fineness. Relative heterosis for kernel length after cooking was positive and significant in five crosses. Heterosis over mid-parent and better parent for kernel elongation was positive and highly significant in six hybrids (see table).

Relative heterosis (di) and heterobeltiosis (dii) in % for kernel characters in selected crosses.^a TNRRI, Aduthurai, India. 1991-92 wet season.

Cross	Kernel length		Kernel L:B ratio		Kernel length after cooking		Kernel elongation	
	di	dii	di	dii	di	dii	di	dii
ADT37/ADT41	-3.1**	-22.1**	-11.4**	-36.9**	2.7*	-16.6**	9.2**	5.2**
ADT39/ADT41	-1.9**	-17.2**	-6.8**	-26.0**	1.4	-14.2**	4.0**	3.3*
ADT39/Kasturi	-2.6**	-16.0**	-11.5**	-29.3**	2.8*	-11.2**	8.8**	8.8**
IR50/Kasturi	0.7*	-5.6**	-5.1**	-15.6**	12.5**	-4.4**	12.2**	11.5**
Improved White Ponni/ADT41	1.9**	-14.7**	-4.1**	-21.5**	13.2**	-3.6**	11.9**	11.9**
Improved White Ponni/Kasturi	-1.2**	-15.5**	-9.2**	-25.2**	3.6*	-9.9**	8.0**	7.3**

*, ** = significant at 1 and 5% level, respectively.

IR50/Kasturi and Improved White Ponni/ADT41 show promise for improving kernel length, kernel length after cooking, and kernel elongation through heterosis breeding. ■

High-yielding somaclonal variants of Basmati 370

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Improving basmati varieties through cross breeding results in recombination of various genes for yield and quality. But

these new combinations often do not yield the desired basmati quality. We have been researching ways to accelerate the improvement of both quality and yield of basmati rices.

We obtained a series of somaclonal variants with desired characteristics. Seeds of Basmati 370 were inoculated on MS medium with 2 mg 2,4-D/liter. Calli were subcultured 12 times on the same

Table 1. Agronomic performance of somaclonal variants.^a NARC, Islamabad, Pakistan.

Variant	Flowering (d)		Plant height (cm)		Tillers/hill (no.)		1,000-grain weight (g)		Fertility (%)	Yield (t/ha)
TF4	114	de	120	f	12	e	17.33	cd	89.0	a
SN85	127	b	140	c	14	cd	16.00	de	65.0	de
SN1-80	129	ab	147	b	14	cd	14.33	e	65.0	de
TF11	115	de	116	g	15	bc	13.67	e	63.3	de
SN12	116	cd	113	h	13	de	19.00	abc	70.0	c
TF8	113	e	123	e	13	de	17.67	bcd	65.0	de
TF9	116	cd	127	d	20	a	17.33	cd	66.3	cd
TF10	118	c	123	e	16	b	16.00	de	61.7	e
Basmati 385	114	de	122	e	15	bc	21.00	a	80.0	b
Basmati 370	130	a	150	a	9	f	20.00	ab	70.0	c
LSD (5%)	2.142		2.187		1.265		2.38		3.514	0.5868
CV (%)	1.05		0.99		5.23		8.08		2.95	9.90

^aMeans in a column followed by the same letter are not significantly different at 5% level by DMRT.